

EFFECTIVENESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' TRAINING IN RELATION TO TEACHERS AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE, THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT, BOHOL

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ABSTRACT

The following research analyzed the Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers' Training about Teachers and School Performance in the Third Congressional District of Bohol through a survey of 1,238 teacher respondents from the selected schools within the Third Congressional District during the school year 2019-2020. The study is utilizing a modified tool by Rahman and Jumani in their study about the relationship between the training of teachers and effective teaching. The survey tool has three main sections, with the first section obtaining the respondent's profile; the second section determines the extent of teachers' training effectiveness in teaching, student needs, student evaluation, classroom management, human relationships, teachers' characteristics, clarity and effectiveness of the presentation, student interest/involvement in learning, and the teacher-student relationship. Moreover, the third section measures the school's level of performance. The questionnaire was pilot-tested on a group of teachers other than the respondents for validity before it was distributed to the actual respondents of the study. The study utilized the descriptive research method and underwent ethics protocol and review before the gathering of data. The protocol required that the researcher undergo the review procedures of the Research Ethics Committee and secure proper permission and consent from the Dean of Graduate Studies and Vice-President of Academics of the university. Statistical tests for the data were weighted mean, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation, Chi-square, ANOVA, SPSS 24, and Scheffe's Test. This study covers eight hundred fifty-one respondents. Most were females and of which most also were married. The teacher respondents also have a Master's Degree in units.

Furthermore, for their teaching experience, most of them were in 0-3 years of service. The findings of each variable (INSET, LAC Session, Division Mass Training, Regional Mass Training, Teachers' Performance and School Performance) wherein the least two-rated statements are the basis for recommendations. Allocate funds for the training of teachers so that all the teachers have equal chances to join the different levels of training. Competencies not covered by a particular quarter should be priority topics to be tackled since higher levels of training have limited slots. Those whom the school administrator sends are obliged to conduct re-echo seminars and develop learners to be independent by integrating higher-order skills and thought-provoking questions. Teachers are encouraged to utilize local resources, report regularly the learners' progress to parents and interpret test results as a basis for enhancement.

Keywords: *Secondary School Teachers, School Performance, Third Congressional District Bohol, Teachers Training, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Education is widely recognized as a fundamental asset for national development, driven primarily by the role of teachers whose responsibilities extend beyond the mere transmission of academic knowledge. Teachers are instrumental not only in fostering intellectual growth but also in shaping students' values, attitudes, and skills, preparing them to be productive leaders of tomorrow. According to Essays UK (2018), knowledge exists in two distinct forms: tacit knowledge, which encompasses personal insights gained through experience, and explicit knowledge, which can be clearly communicated and systematically transferred. Effective teaching, therefore, involves the crucial skill of transforming tacit knowledge into explicit instructional strategies to facilitate meaningful learning experiences.

Continuous professional development through systematic and structured teacher training has been identified as essential to achieving academic excellence and maintaining educational quality (Asghar et al., 2022). Globally, empirical evidence supports that teacher training programs significantly enhance teachers' self-efficacy, instructional effectiveness, and overall performance in educational settings. For instance, in the United States, research by Darling et al. (2005) demonstrates that certified and trained teachers consistently outperform their untrained counterparts. Similarly, in Canada, professional training has been found to significantly reduce teachers' apprehension towards public speaking while enhancing their confidence and effectiveness in classroom instruction (Boman, 2013). Finland's educational system further underscores the importance of training, with research indicating that teachers' belief in their students' abilities, shaped through comprehensive professional development, directly contributes to higher academic achievements (Talvio et al., 2015).

In Germany, the implementation of extensive school-based training and holistic approaches has positively impacted family dynamics, school effectiveness, and student

learning outcomes (Fischer & Theis, 2014). Additionally, Swedish experiences have confirmed that teacher training involving cognitive and behavioral methods markedly improves student self-control, social competencies, and academic motivation (Kimber & Sandell, 2009). Collectively, these international findings highlight the essential role of structured professional training in elevating teaching effectiveness and improving student performance.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) actively recognizes the significance of teacher training programs and annually invests substantial financial resources at national, regional, and division levels. Training mechanisms such as Learning Action Cells (LAC) have been institutionalized to support continuous professional growth among Filipino educators, fostering collaborative problem-solving and enhancing teaching skills (Nieve, 2021); Head Foundation, 2019). According to Magno (2012), Filipino educators traditionally emphasize learner-centered approaches; however, he cautions that without effective training, even robust teaching methodologies may fail to produce optimal academic results. Bustos (2008) further emphasizes the cultural predispositions of Filipino teachers, highlighting the importance of personality-based traits and teaching competencies nurtured through sustained professional development.

Supporting these perspectives, Goldhaber (2011) and Sirait (2016) assert that teacher quality, developed through systematic training, constitutes one of the most crucial determinants of student learning and school performance. Bullough (2009) also identifies formal and informal professional development opportunities as critical components of teacher growth. McDonald and Boud (2003) suggest that training teachers in self-assessment strategies significantly impacts student performance outcomes, while Bressoux (2016) highlights that training is particularly beneficial for novice educators. Furthermore, Asiyai (2016) stresses that teachers who participate in structured in-service training programs often perceive substantial benefits regarding their instructional practice.

Despite these extensive studies, a gap remains in systematically evaluating the effectiveness of training programs, specifically within the context of secondary education in the Philippines, particularly within localized settings. Addressing this research gap, the current study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of secondary school teacher training programs concerning teacher competencies and school performance in the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol during the academic year 2019-2020. By employing a comparative analytical approach, this research seeks to determine the actual impact of existing training initiatives on teacher effectiveness and educational outcomes, offering insights to enhance both policy frameworks and instructional practices.

The study's theoretical foundation is grounded in several educational and psychological theories, including Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (1978), highlighting guided learning interactions; Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943), emphasizing intrinsic motivation; Cognitive Evaluation Theory, distinguishing intrinsic from extrinsic motivational factors; Skinner's Classroom Management Theory, focusing

on reinforcement principles in effective teaching; Homans' Social Exchange Theory, addressing relational dynamics between educators and learners; Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, underscoring learning through reflective experience; Schramm's Model of Communication (1954), articulating the necessity of effective communication in instructional settings; and Astin's Theory of Student Involvement (1999), linking engagement directly to educational success.

Moreover, the research adheres to and aligns explicitly with relevant Philippine educational policies and laws, including Republic Act No. 7784 (Strengthening Teacher Education), Republic Act No. 7836 (Philippine Professionalization Act of 1994), Republic Act No. 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), and DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016 (Learning Action Cell). Collectively, these regulations underscore the governmental mandate and commitment to quality education through sustained teacher professional development initiatives.

Ultimately, this study endeavors not only to evaluate existing training mechanisms but also to provide meaningful, actionable recommendations for strengthening teacher development practices. By doing so, the research aims to enhance educational standards, foster improved student outcomes, and contribute significantly to both local and national educational policy development, benefiting educators, learners, and the broader community.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of secondary school teachers' training to school performance of the Third Congressional District of Bohol during the school year 2019-2020. The findings of this study served as the basis for proposing an enhancement program.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the secondary school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex;
 - 1.3. Civil Status;
 - 1.4. Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. Number of years in teaching?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of teachers' training in the following?
 - 2.1. In-Service training;
 - 2.2. LAC (Learning Action Cell);
 - 2.3. Division Mass Training of Teachers;
 - 2.4. Regional Mass Training of Teachers?
3. What is the level of teachers' performance in the following dimensions?
 - 3.1. Teaching;
 - 3.2. Students' need;
 - 3.3. Students' evaluation;
 - 3.4. Classroom management;

- 3.5. Human relationship;
- 3.6. Teacher characteristics;
- 3.7. Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation;
- 3.8. Students' interest in learning;
- 3.9. Teacher-Student relationship?
- 4. What is the school performance as to:
 - 4.1. Promotion rate;
 - 4.2. Failure rate;
 - 4.3. Retention rate;
 - 4.4. Drop-out rate?
- 5. Is there a significant degree of relationships between teachers' profile and the following:
 - 5.1. Level of the effectiveness of teachers' training;
 - 5.2. Level of teachers' performance;
 - 5.3. School performance?
- 6. Is there a significant degree of correlation between the following variables:
 - 6.1. Level of effectiveness and teachers' performance;
 - 6.2. Level of Effectiveness and School Performance;
 - 6.3. Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Performance and School Performance?
- 7. Is there a significant degree of variance in the following:
 - 7.1. Level of effectiveness in the different pieces of training;
 - 7.2. Level of teachers' performance in different dimensions;
 - 7.3. Level of school performance in the various indicators?
- 8. Based on the findings, what enhancement program could be proposed to address the phenomenon?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed the quantitative descriptive method of research with the questionnaire as the main instrument to collect the data needed in the study. The survey was used to collect the respondents' perceptions and responses.

This study made use of universal- purposive sampling techniques for the respondents. It involved a complete enumeration of all the secondary school teachers and school administrators of the Third Congressional District of Bohol Division in the Department of Education.

Research Environment

Bohol has been divided into three congressional districts since 1907, although the district configurations hindered the restoration of the House of Representatives in 1987.

This study covered the schools of Third Congressional District of Bohol which included the following municipalities: Alicia, Anda, Batuan, Bilar, Candijay, Carmen, Dimiao, Duero, Garcia Hernandez, Guindulman, Jagna, Lila, Loay, Loboc, Mabini, Pilar, Sevilla, Sierra Bullones, Valencia.

Research Respondents

The study made use of a complete enumeration of the respondents. It covered specifically the secondary school teachers of the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol. For the school year 2019-2020, there were eight hundred fifty-one (851) secondary school teachers.

Distribution of Respondents
n=851

Municipality	Teachers
Alicia	81
Anda	40
Batuan	26
Bilar	52
Candijay	28
Carmen	62
Dimiao	25
Duero	36
Garcia Hernandez	42
Guindulman	42
Jagna	26
Lila	48
Loay	28
Loboc	18
Mabini	55
Pilar	28
Sevilla	26
Sierra Bullones	84
Valencia	114
Total	851

Research Instrument

The researcher adapted a survey tool that had three main sections. The first section gathered the respondents' profile. The second questionnaire was pilot tested to a group of teachers other than the respondents for validity before it was distributed to the actual respondents of the study. Furthermore, it determined the extent of teachers' training effectiveness in teaching, student needs, student evaluation, classroom management, human relationship, teachers' characteristics, clarity and effectiveness of presentation, student interest/ involvement in learning, and the teacher-student relationship. The third section was for the school's level of school performance. The questionnaire was a modified tool from the study of Rahman et al. (2007). Efforts were

made by the researcher to authorize the use of the survey instrument through electronic mail.

Gathering of Data

The researcher first prepared a letter of request and secured approval from the Dean of the Graduate Studies of the University of Bohol for the distribution of questionnaires to the respondents. A similar request was submitted to the Vice President for Academics for final approval of the questionnaire distribution. Prior to administering the questionnaires to school principals or headteachers, permission was also obtained from the district supervisor to conduct the study in all schools within the 3rd Congressional District of Bohol. The distribution of the instruments was coursed through the school principals, who were given a specific period for the respondents to answer and for the retrieval of the accomplished forms. The retrieval of the instruments was carried out as soon as the allotted period had ended, and the respondents had submitted their responses. The data were then tallied and processed by the researcher, and the ungrouped data were forwarded to a statistician for further analysis and interpretation. Finally, the results were discussed based on the tables and the data analysis.

Data Analysis

In the analysis and interpretation of data, the following formula used:

Weighted Mean. This technique is used to measure the central tendency where some values are given importance over others.

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. To ascertain the relationship between the effectiveness of secondary school teachers training about school performance, the data subjected to the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation.

Chi-square. To test the significant degree of relationship in the different dimensions on the level of teachers' training effectiveness, the extent of teachers' attendance, and level of school performance, the data subjected to Chi-square used.

ANOVA. To determine the degree of variance in the different dimensions on the level of teachers' training effectiveness, the extent of teachers' attendance, and level of school performance must be considered.

Scheffe's' Test. To further test the significant variance in the perceptions of the secondary school teachers and their school administrators on their responses on the level of teachers' training effectiveness, the extent of teachers' attendance, and level of school performance, the Scheffe's' Test was used.

RESULTS

The needed information of the study was gathered by conducting a survey eight hundred fifty-one (851) teachers of 3rd Congressional District of Bohol. The outcomes are herein presented, analyzed and interpreted under the various headings that correspond to the various aspects of the problems.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents
n = 851

1.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
20 – 24	66	7.8	5.0
25 – 29	207	24.3	1.0
30 – 34	143	16.8	4.0
35 – 39	150	17.6	2.0
40 – 44	144	16.9	3.0
45 – 49	53	6.2	6.0
50 – 54	44	5.2	7.0
55 – 59	31	3.6	8.0
60 – 64	13	1.5	9.0
Total	851	100%	
1.2 Sex			
Male	189	22.2	2.0
Female	662	77.8	1.0
Total	851	100%	
1.3 Civil Status			
Single	252	29.6	2.0
Married	599	70.4	1.0
Total	851	100%	
1.4 Highest Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree	302	35.5	2.0
With Master's Units	420	49.4	1.0
Master's Degree	88	10.3	3.0
With Doctoral Units	34	4.0	4.0
Doctoral Degree	7	.8	5.0
Total	851	100%	
1.4 Number of Years in Teaching			
0 - 3 years	236	27.7	1.0
4 - 6 years	209	24.6	2.0
7 - 9 years	72	8.5	5.0
10 - 12 years	97	11.4	3.0
13 - 15 years	74	8.7	4.0
16 - 18 years	51	6.0	6.0
19 - 21 years	37	4.3	7.0
22 - 24 years	36	4.2	8.0
25 - 27 years	19	2.2	9.0
28 - 30 years	8	.9	11.0
31 - 33 years	10	1.2	10.0
34 - 36 years	2	.2	12.0
Total	851	100%	

The majority of respondents were aged 25–29 (24.3%), indicating a relatively young teaching workforce in the Third Congressional District of Bohol. Most were female (77.8%) and married (70.4%), which reflects common demographic trends in the teaching profession.

In terms of educational attainment, nearly half (49.4%) had earned Master’s units, while 35.5% held a bachelor’s degree. Only a small portion had completed a master’s or doctoral degree. Regarding teaching experience, most respondents (27.7%) had been teaching for 0–3 years, further highlighting the dominance of early-career teachers in the respondent pool.

Table 2
Level of Effectiveness of Teacher’s Training
n=851

1. In- Service Trainings (INSET)	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Modular teaching is stressful.	3.98	.620	VS	3
2. The mass production of modules has made me feel exhausted.	3.94	.665	VS	5
3. The distribution and retrieval of modules is time-consuming.	4.10	.659	VS	1
4. Module checking is quite confusing.	3.97	.688	VS	4
5. Lesson feedbacking in modular teaching is very challenging.	4.04	.674	VS	2
Composite Mean	4.01	.551	VS	
2. Learning Action Cell (LAC)	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Identify instructional problems.	4.01	.721	VS	1
2. Assess students’ least mastered skills.	3.99	.707	VS	2
3. Identify further training on subject-matter content.	3.84	.750	VS	5
4. Determine alternative strategies and solutions encountered in the classroom.	3.91	.713	VS	3
5. Enhance teacher competence in the use of strategies.	3.91	.720	VS	4
Composite Mean	3.93	.649	VS	
3. Division Mass Training	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Training objectives were met.	3.93	.756	VS	3
2. Relevance of activity to improve job.	3.95	.762	VS	2
3. Appropriateness of training methodologies.	3.92	.761	VS	4
4. Opportunities to participate in discussions.	3.98	1.61	VS	1
5. Effectiveness of Training Management.	3.89	.772	VS	5
Composite Mean	3.93	.760	VS	
4. Regional Mass Training	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Provide teachers with concrete understanding of the curriculum frameworks, learning plans and competencies, teaching plans and assessments.	3.93	.797	VS	1
2. Integrate competencies needed by teachers in the effective implementation of the curriculum.	3.89	.797	VS	2
3. Understand the significance of the individual differences of child and to take appropriate steps for their optimum development.	3.88	.789	VS	4
4. Enable teachers to maximize the use of instructional materials.	3.89	.791	VS	3
5. Promote a culture of collegial and collaborative learning among teachers in the entire region.	3.88	.810	VS	5
Composite Mean	3.89	.742	VS	
Overall Mean	3.94	VS		

Among the training categories, In-Service Trainings (INSET) received the highest composite mean (M = 4.01), followed by Learning Action Cell (LAC) and Division Mass Training (both M = 3.93), and Regional Mass Training (M = 3.89). All were interpreted as *Very Satisfactory*.

INSET was particularly noted for addressing challenges in modular teaching such as module distribution and lesson feedbacking. LAC sessions were valued for helping teachers identify instructional gaps and improve classroom strategies. Division and Regional trainings were also positively rated for their relevance, interactivity, and support in curriculum implementation.

The overall mean rating of 3.94 indicates that teacher training programs in the Third Congressional District of Bohol were perceived as highly effective in enhancing teaching competencies and addressing instructional needs during modular distance learning.

Table 3
Summary on the Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

Components	CM	SD	INT	RANK
In- Service Trainings (INSET)	4.0063	.55137	VS	1
Learning Action Cell (LAC)	3.9321	.64879	VS	3
Division Mass Training	3.9337	.76033	VS	2
Regional Mass Training	3.8938	.74179	VS	4
Overall Mean	3.9415	.55487	VS	

Table 3 shows that among the training types, In-Service Trainings (INSET) received the highest effectiveness rating (M = 4.01), followed by Division Mass Training (M = 3.93), Learning Action Cell (LAC) (M = 3.93), and Regional Mass Training (M = 3.89). All components were rated *Very Satisfactory*.

The results suggest that INSETs were most effective, likely due to the uniform and direct delivery of content to all participants. In contrast, Regional Mass Trainings ranked lowest, possibly due to limited participant access, where only select representatives attended. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of inclusive and consistently delivered training programs to maximize their impact on teaching effectiveness.

Table 4
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

Components	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Fair	9	1.1	4
Satisfactory	128	15.0	3
Very Satisfactory	447	52.5	1
Excellent	267	31.4	2
Overall Mean	3.9415	.55487	

Table 4 shows the level of effectiveness of teachers' training as it is interpreted as Fair, Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory and Excellent. Based on the result, the level of effectiveness of teachers' training is Very Satisfactory with a frequency of four hundred forty-seven or (52.5%) ranked first. Next is Excellent with a frequency of two hundred sixty-seven or (31.4%), Satisfactory with a frequency of one hundred twenty-eight or (15.0%) and lastly Fair which is ranked fourth with nine frequency or (1.1%).

Table 5
Level of Teachers' Performance
n=851

Statement	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Training Effectiveness in terms of Teaching				
1. The teacher selects appropriate teaching method relevant to the course content.	4.1974	.66936	E	4
2. The teacher plans effective lessons.	4.2526	.65859	E	3
3. The teacher prepares the use of Audio-Visual aids for teaching.	4.0893	.69892	VS	5
4. The teacher promotes discussion about subject-matter.	4.2926	.65811	E	2
5. The teacher promotes teamwork and sharing of ideas of his/her students.	4.3102	.67571	E	1
Composite Mean	4.2284	.56209	E	
2. Training Effectiveness in terms of Student Needs				
1. The teacher stimulates students to think in a critical way.	4.1610	.67296	VS	6
2. The teacher produces independent learners.	4.0870	.71089	VS	8
3. The teacher helps the students to understand important ideas.	4.2867	.65623	E	1
4. The teacher helps students to organize their work.	4.2350	.67301	E	2
5. The teacher keeps students constructively engaged in their work.	4.2268	.68016	E	3
6. The teacher adjusts class activities to learning needs of individual students.	4.1904	.68699	VS	5
7. The teacher develops student observation techniques.	4.1375	.69529	VS	7
8. The teacher arouses students' interest in learning.	4.2162	.66705	E	4
Composite Mean	4.1943	.57704	VS	
3. Level of Teachers' Performance in terms of Students' Evaluation				
1. The teacher properly uses various evaluation techniques/tests.	4.1821	.66223	VS	1
2. The teacher gives students proper class work assignments.	4.0611	.72989	VS	3
3. The teacher gives students proper homework assignments.	3.8179	.83790	VS	5
4. The teacher shows and indicates the rate of progress to each student.	4.1410	.66605	VS	2
5. The teacher points out their weaknesses and strengths to students.	4.0576	.67752	VS	4
Composite Mean	4.0519	.58962	VS	
4. Teacher Training and Classroom Management				
1. The teacher has proper management of class time	4.2597	.68737	E	3
2. The teacher has proper management of classroom space.	4.2080	.67054	E	5
3. The teacher has proper management of materials and equipment.	4.1105	.68395	VS	8
4. The teacher has proper record keeping	4.3173	.68970	E	1
5. The teacher establishes classroom routines and procedures.	4.3067	.66239	E	2
6. The teacher develops proper student behavior in the classroom.	4.2538	.67316	E	4
7. The teacher effectively uses rewards for increasing desirable behavior.	4.0588	.65355	VS	9
8. The teacher uses challenging, positive remarks.	4.1951	.63396	E	6
9. The teacher carefully employs and uses anecdotes and stories.	3.9201	.68648	VS	10
10. The teacher effectively uses punishment for decreasing undesirable behavior.	3.5770	.92908	VS	11
11. The teacher provides a climate for students to learn.	4.1363	.67579	VS	7
Composite Mean	4.1224	.52707	VS	
5. Teacher Training and Human Relationship				
	WM	SD	INT	Rank

1. The teacher establishes appropriate relationship with students.	4.2949	.66595	E	4
2. The teacher supports and cares for his/her students.	4.4007	.64202	E	1
3. The teacher helps students develop better relationships with each other.	4.3443	.64909	E	2
4. The teacher provides situations where students can learn from each other.	4.2973	.66136	E	3
Composite Mean	4.3343	.58888	E	
6. Teacher Characteristics	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Teacher has come to classroom on time.	4.3102	.66341	E	5
2. Teacher is self-confident during instruction.	4.4042	.63704	E	2
3. Teacher shows good manners in the classroom.	4.4219	.62831	E	1
4. Teacher properly uses classroom resources.	4.3043	.64185	E	6
5. Teacher uses good examples to explain concepts.	4.3408	.64277	E	3
6. Teacher is actively helpful when you have problems.	4.3161	.64349	E	4
7. Teacher quickly provides test results.	4.1633	.66536	VS	7
Composite Mean	4.3228	.54519	E	
7. Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. The students understand easily what the teachers are saying.	4.0118	.67552	VS	10
2. The teachers can communicate effectively.	4.2374	.67914	E	3
3. The teachers can speak audibly and clearly.	4.2985	.64915	E	1
4. The teachers display a clear understanding of course topics.	4.2761	.64544	E	2
5. The teachers can simplify difficult materials.	4.1563	.66529	VS	7
6. The teachers explain experiments and assignments clearly.	4.1763	.67698	VS	6
7. The teachers can talk at a pace suitable for maximum comprehension.	4.2056	.67824	E	4
8. The teachers draw and explain diagrams effectively.	4.1328	.69112	VS	8
9. The teachers write legibly on the blackboard.	4.1962	.69131	E	5
10. The teachers have no distracting peculiarities	4.0870	.68904	VS	9
Composite Mean	4.1778	.57050	VS	
8. Student Interest/ Involvement in Learning	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Teachers sense when students are bored.	4.2773	.68647	E	1
2. Teachers stimulate interest in the course.	4.2244	.65989	E	4
3. Teachers display enthusiasm when teaching.	4.2750	.66656	E	2
4. Teachers use many methods to involve you in learning.	4.1927	.66190	VS	6
5. Teachers motivate you to do further independent study.	4.1998	.67392	E	5
6. Teachers have stimulated my thinking.	4.1434	.66022	VS	7
7. Teachers allow me to present my own views in class.	4.2703	.65245	E	3
Composite Mean	4.2261	.57132	E	
9. Teacher-student Relationship	WM	SD	INT	Rank
1. Teachers accept good suggestions.	4.4407	.65418	E	2
2. Teachers readily maintain rapport with the class.	4.3913	.64780	E	3
3. Teachers identify each student by name.	4.3137	.71227	E	4
4. Teachers provide guidance in solutions of various problems.	4.3008	.65708	E	5
5. Teachers come to classroom with smiling and agreeable faces.	4.2644	.66995	E	6
6. Teachers treat all the students equally.	4.4583	.65912	E	1
Composite Mean	4.3614	.58629	E	
Overall Mean	4.2241	E		

The overall mean rating of 4.22 indicates that teachers in the Third Congressional District of Bohol performed at an *Excellent* level across various teaching dimensions.

The highest-rated areas were Teacher-Student Relationship (M = 4.36) and Human Relationships (M = 4.33), showing strong interpersonal connections and care for students. Teacher Characteristics (M = 4.32) and Student Interest/Involvement (M = 4.23) also ranked high, reflecting professionalism and effective student engagement.

Meanwhile, Teaching Practices (M = 4.23), Student Needs (M = 4.19), Classroom Management (M = 4.12), and Presentation Clarity (M = 4.18) were consistently rated *Excellent* or *Very Satisfactory*, indicating solid instructional delivery and communication.

Student Evaluation had the lowest composite mean (M = 4.05), still rated *Very Satisfactory*, suggesting that while teachers use appropriate assessment methods, improvements could be made in assigning and managing student work.

Overall, the results highlight teachers' competence in fostering a supportive learning environment, delivering quality instruction, and maintaining strong classroom and professional standards.

Table 6
Summary on the Teaching Performance
n=851

Categories	CM	SD	INT	RANK
A. Training effectiveness in term of teaching	4.2284	.56209	E	4
B. Training effectiveness in term of student needs	4.1943	.57704	VS	6
C. Training effectiveness in term of students' evaluation	4.0519	.58962	VS	9
D. Teacher training and classroom management	4.1224	.52707	VS	8
E. Teacher training and human relationship	4.3343	.58888	E	2
F. Teacher characteristics	4.3228	.54519	E	3
G. Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation	4.1778	.57050	VS	7
H. Student Interest/ Involvement in Learning	4.2261	.57132	E	5
I. Teacher-student relationship	4.3614	.58629	E	1
Overall Mean	4.2241	.50409	E	

The overall composite mean of 4.22 indicates an *Excellent* level of teaching performance among the respondents. Among the nine categories evaluated, Teacher-Student Relationship ranked highest (M = 4.36), followed by Human Relationship (M = 4.33) and Teacher Characteristics (M = 4.32), all interpreted as *Excellent*. These findings highlight teachers' strength in fostering positive interpersonal relationships and maintaining professional behavior.

On the other hand, the lowest-ranked dimensions were Training Effectiveness in Terms of Student Evaluation (M = 4.05), Classroom Management (M = 4.12), and Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation (M = 4.18), all rated *Very Satisfactory*. This suggests that while teachers are performing well, these areas present opportunities for further development and training support.

Overall, the results affirm the positive impact of training on teaching performance, especially in relational and professional aspects, while indicating the need for enhancement in assessment practices and classroom management strategies.

Table 7
Level of Teachers' Performance
n=851

	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Satisfactory	61	7.2	3
Very Satisfactory	348	40.9	2
Excellent	442	51.9	1
Total	851	100.0	

Table 7 shows the level of teachers' performance of which the result showed an Excellent result with four hundred forty-four frequency or (51.9%) ranked first, it is then followed by Very Satisfactory with three hundred forty—eight frequency or (40.9%), and lastly Satisfactory with sixty-one frequency or (7.2%). This simply implies that teachers' training does an excellent part within terms of teachers' performance.

Table 8
School Performance as to Promotion, Failure, Retention, and Drop-Out Rate
n=851

A. Promotion Rate	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Very Poor	1	.1	5
Poor	3	.4	4
Fair	37	4.3	3
Good	562	66.0	1
Excellent	248	29.1	2
Total	851	100.0	
Mean	4.2374	G	
Std. Deviation	.55099		
B. Failure Rate	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Very Poor	188	22.1	3
Poor	305	35.8	1
Fair	196	23.0	2
Good	150	17.6	4
Excellent	12	1.4	5
Total	851	100.0	
Mean	2.4042	P	
Std. Deviation	1.05883		
C. Retention Rate	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Very Poor	188	22.1	3.0
Poor	213	25.0	2.0
Fair	127	14.9	4.0

Good	253	29.7	1.0
Excellent	70	8.2	5.0
Total	851	100.0	
Mean	2.7697	F	
Std. Deviation	1.30738		
D. Drop-out Rate	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Very Poor	277	32.5	2.0
Poor	284	33.4	1.0
Fair	152	17.9	3.0
Good	128	15.0	4.0
Excellent	10	1.2	5.0
Total	851	100.0	
Mean	2.1892	P	
Std. Deviation	1.08495		

School performance was assessed through four key indicators: promotion, failure, retention, and drop-out rates.

The Promotion Rate yielded a mean of 4.24, interpreted as *Good*, with the majority of responses falling under *Good* (66.0%) and *Excellent* (29.1%). This indicates that most students successfully advanced to the next grade level, reflecting effective instructional delivery.

Conversely, the Failure Rate had a mean of 2.40 (*Poor*), with a large proportion of responses under *Poor* (35.8%) and *Very Poor* (22.1%). This suggests that a considerable number of students did not meet academic requirements, pointing to a need for academic support and remediation.

For Retention Rate, the composite mean of 2.77 was interpreted as *Fair*. While 29.7% rated it *Good*, notable percentages still rated it *Poor* (25.0%) or *Very Poor* (22.1%), indicating moderate retention and the need to strengthen efforts to keep students enrolled.

The Drop-Out Rate was rated *Poor* with a mean of 2.19. The highest responses were *Poor* (33.4%) and *Very Poor* (32.5%), revealing a significant concern in student attrition. This underscores the urgency for intervention programs to address drop-outs and encourage school completion.

Table 9
Level of School Performance
n=851

	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Very Poor	106	12.5	5.0
Poor	166	19.5	4.0
Fair	315	37.0	2.0
Good	264	31.0	3.0

Excellent	851	100.0	1.0
Total	3.7186	Good	
Mean	.72849		
Std. Deviation	106	12.5	5.0

The overall school performance is depicted on table 9. Based on the result, the school performance has a mean of 3.7186 and a standard deviation of .72849 interpreted as Good. The rankings are as follows: Excellent with eight hundred fifty-one or (100.0%); Fair with three hundred fifteen or (37.0%); Good with two hundred sixty-four or (31.0%); Poor one hundred sixty-six for the frequency or (19.5%) and Very Poor with one-hundred six or (12.5%).

The interpretation of a "Good" overall mean suggests that while the school is performing well in key indicators, there is still room for improvement. The presence of notable percentages in the Fair, Poor, and Very Poor categories signals existing gaps that must be addressed. These may include issues related to instructional quality, learner outcomes, or school management. Strengthening teacher support systems, improving student retention strategies, and enhancing training programs may contribute to elevating overall performance toward an Excellent level.

Table 10
Test of Normality
n=851

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			Results
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	.085	851	.000	.984	851	.000	Skewed
Teaching Performance	.062	851	.000	.961	851	.000	Skewed
Promotion Rate	.375	851	0.000	.701	851	.000	Skewed
Failure Rate	.228	851	.000	.885	851	.000	Skewed
Retention Rate	.206	851	.000	.882	851	.000	Skewed
Drop-Out Rate	.228	851	.000	.856	851	.000	Skewed
School Performance	.158	851	.000	.948	851	.000	Skewed

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 10 presents the test of normality using the Kolmogorov Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk tests. The results indicate that the variables: effectiveness of teachers' training, teaching performance, promotion rate, failure rate, retention rate, and drop-out rate, exhibit skewed distributions.

This means the data are not perfectly symmetrical, suggesting deviations from normality. The skewness implies that these variables may be interrelated, indicating

possible underlying connections among the different aspects of school performance and teacher effectiveness.

Table 11
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Level of Effectiveness of
Teachers' Training
n=851

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	31.588 ^a	24	.138
Likelihood Ratio	33.841	24	.088
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.562	1	.109
N of Valid Cases			
	851		

		Age									Total
		20 – 24	25 – 29	30 – 34	35 – 39	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59	60 - 64	
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	Fair	1	5	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	9
	Satisfactory	17	31	25	24	16	9	4	1	1	128
	Very Satisfactory	27	108	73	74	77	26	32	23	7	447
	Excellent	21	63	44	51	51	17	8	7	5	267
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Table 11 presents the significant degree of level of effectiveness of teachers' training and age profile. The result showed that four hundred forty-seven respondents' responses to Very Satisfactory as to the level of effectiveness to teachers' training. Two hundred sixty-seven for Excellent; one hundred eighty-one for Satisfactory; and 9 for fair. This simply implies that half of the respondents agree that of all sorts of age brackets among teachers they are very satisfied of the effectiveness of teachers' training. The data where then further subjected to Chi-square Test of which the result revealed a 12 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14. There is a significant degree of relationship between the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and age.

Table 12
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	Fair	5	4	9
	Satisfactory	25	103	128
	Very Satisfactory	91	356	447
	Excellent	68	199	267
Total		189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.852 ^a	3	.031
Likelihood Ratio	7.732	3	.052
Linear-by-Linear Association	.524	1	.469
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 1 cell (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.00.

Table 12 showed the significant degree of relationship between level of effectiveness of teachers' training and sex profile. The result revealed that four hundred forty-seven of the respondents regardless of sex agree to a Very Satisfactory rating on the effectiveness of teachers' training and sex profile, followed with the following two hundred sixty-seven for Excellent, one hundred twenty-eight for Satisfactory and nine for

Fair. The data were further tested using the Chi-square Test of which 1 cell (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.00. With-in terms of sex profile, most of the respondents have showed that there is a significant degree of relationship on the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and sex.

Table 13
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Level of
Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	Fair	7	2	9
	Satisfactory	47	81	128
	Very Satisfactory	124	323	447
	Excellent	74	193	267
Total		252	599	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.331 ^a	3	.002
Likelihood Ratio	13.113	3	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.036	1	.014
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 1 cells (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.67.

Table 13 shows the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and civil status. The result revealed that four hundred forty-seven of the respondents regardless of their civil status agree to a Very Satisfactory rating on the effectiveness of teachers' training and civil status, followed with the following two hundred sixty-seven for Excellent, one hundred twenty-eight for Satisfactory and nine for Fair, of which it is further tested using the chi-square test which also shows that a 1 cells (12.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.67. This means that regardless of teachers' civil status, there is really an impact for the teachers who attended or participated in training.

Table 14
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	Fair	1	5	1	2	0	9
	Satisfactory	48	64	12	4	0	128
	Very Satisfactory	157	228	44	13	5	447
	Excellent	96	123	31	15	2	267
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.671 ^a	12	.207
Likelihood Ratio	13.363	12	.343
Linear-by-Linear Association	.277	1	.599
<hr/>			
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 8 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07.

Table 14 shows the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and the highest educational attainment. It is then based on the result that teachers' responses to Very Satisfactory as to the level of effectiveness to teachers' training. Two hundred sixty-seven for Excellent; one hundred eighty-one for Satisfactory; and 9 for fair. It is then further tested with Chi-square test which shows that 8 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .07. This simply implies that half of the respondents agree that the highest educational attainment among teachers is very satisfied with the effectiveness of teachers' training.

Table 15
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Number of Years in Teaching and
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3 years	4 - 6 years	7 - 9 years	10 - 12 years	13 - 15 years	16 - 18 years	19 - 21 years	22 - 24 years	25 - 27 years	28 - 30 years	31 - 33 years		34 - 36 years
Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training	Fair	5	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
	Satisfactory	35	42	11	14	13	3	3	5	1	0	1	0	128
	Very Satisfactory	120	110	35	53	27	31	23	19	13	6	8	2	447
	Excellent	76	54	26	29	34	17	11	12	5	2	1	0	267
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.404 ^a	33	.313
Likelihood Ratio	42.225	33	.130
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.128	1	.077
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 21 cells (43.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

Table 15 shows the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and number of years in teaching. The result revealed that four hundred forty-seven agree to a Very Satisfactory rating on the effectiveness of teachers' training and number of years in teaching, followed with the following two hundred sixty-seven for Excellent, one hundred twenty-eight for Satisfactory and nine for Fair, of which it is further tested using the chi-square test which also shows that at 21 cells (43.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02. This means that most of the teachers, either they are new to the field or seniors, already have a compatriot idea that teachers training matters most.

To sum it up with regards to the level of the effectiveness of teachers' training and the teachers' profile, all have a uniform response that age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment and number of years in teaching have a significant relationship to the level of effectiveness of teachers' training. These simply imply that teachers who undergo further trainings will truly be benefited and such will result to a Very Satisfactory performance in teaching.

Table 16
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Level of Teachers’
Performance
n=851

		Age								Total	
		20 - 24	25 – 29	30 – 34	35 - 39	40 – 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59		60 - 64
Level of Teachers’ Performance	Satisfactory	3	20	11	11	10	3	2	1	0	61
	Very Satisfactory	30	70	62	62	57	27	18	16	6	348
	Excellent	33	117	70	77	77	23	24	14	7	442
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.405 ^a	16	.716
Likelihood Ratio	13.521	16	.634
Linear-by-Linear Association	.000	1	.986
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 5 cells (18.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .93.

Understanding the relationship between teacher demographics and their performance is essential in assessing factors that influence educational outcomes. Table 16 presents the significant degree of relationship between teachers’ profile and the level of teachers’ performance. The results showed that 442 teachers gave an Excellent remark on the relationship between teachers’ age and their level of performance. This was followed by 348 who rated it as Very Satisfactory, and 61 as Satisfactory.

To further validate these results, a chi-square test was conducted, revealing that 5 cells (18.5%) had an expected count less than 5, with the minimum expected count at 0.93. Despite this, the results imply that age is not a hindrance to effective teaching performance. Teachers across different age groups are capable of delivering high-quality instruction, demonstrating that professional competence and performance are not limited by age but are instead shaped by experience, training, and commitment to the teaching profession.

Table 17
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Level of Teachers’
Performance
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Level of Teachers’ Performance	Satisfactory	13	48	61
	Very Satisfactory	73	275	348
	Excellent	103	339	442
Total		189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.640 ^a	2	.726
Likelihood Ratio	.641	2	.726
Linear-by-Linear Association	.504	1	.478
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 13.55.

Table 17 presents the significant degree relationship between teachers’ sex profile and level of teachers’ performance. The result showed that four hundred forty-two teachers give an Excellent remark on the relationship between teachers’ sex and the level of teachers’ performance. It is then followed by Very Satisfactory with three hundred forty-eight and Satisfactory with sixty-one. It is further tested using the chi-square test which revealed that 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 13.55. This indicates that both male and female may render an Excellent performance in their teaching performance.

Table 18
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Level of Teachers’
Performance
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Level of Teachers’ Performance	Satisfactory	22	39	61
	Very Satisfactory	101	247	348
	Excellent	129	313	442

1488

Total	252	599	851
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Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.315 ^a	2	.518
Likelihood Ratio	1.271	2	.530
Linear-by-Linear Association	.489	1	.484
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 18.06.

Table 18 shows the significant degree relationship between teachers' civil status and level of teachers' performance. The result showed that four hundred forty-two teachers give an Excellent remark on the relationship between teachers' sex and the level of teachers' performance. It is then followed by Very Satisfactory with three hundred forty-eight and Satisfactory with sixty-one. It is further tested using the chi-square test which revealed that 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 18.06. Both married and single teachers perform excellently in teaching as indicated in the result.

Table 19
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and
Level of Teachers' Performance
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Level of Teachers' Performance	Satisfactory	30	23	4	4	0	61
	Very Satisfactory	108	191	39	8	2	348
	Excellent	164	206	45	22	5	442
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.961 ^a	8	.031
Likelihood Ratio	17.594	8	.024
Linear-by-Linear Association	.874	1	.350
N of Valid Cases	851		

1489

a. 4 cells (26.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50.

Table 19 shows the significant degree relationship between teachers' highest educational attainment and level of teachers' performance. The result presents four hundred forty-two teachers give an Excellent remark on the relationship between teachers' sex and the level of teachers' performance. It is then followed by Very Satisfactory with three hundred forty-eight and Satisfactory with sixty-one. It is further tested using the chi-square test 4 cells (26.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .50. This means that whatever educational attainment a teacher is, he or she stills performs Excellent in their teaching performance.

Table 20
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Number of years in Teaching and Level of Teachers' Performance
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3 years	4 - 6 years	7 - 9 years	10 - 12 years	13 - 15 years	16 - 18 years	19 - 21 years	22 - 24 years	25 - 27 years	28 - 30 years	31 - 33 years		34 - 36 years
Level of Teachers' Performance	Satisfactory	14	24	6	5	6	2	1	2	0	0	1	0	61
	Very Satisfactory	90	87	32	40	29	17	19	17	8	3	4	2	348
	Excellent	132	98	34	52	39	32	17	17	11	5	5	0	442
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.371 ^a	22	.560
Likelihood Ratio	22.615	22	.424
Linear-by-Linear Association	.301	1	.583
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 12 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14.

Table 20 shows the significant degree relationship between teacher's number of years in teaching and level of teachers' performance. The result presents four hundred

forty-two teachers give an Excellent remark on the relationship between teachers' sex and the level of teachers' performance. It is then followed by Very Satisfactory with three hundred forty-eight and Satisfactory with sixty-one. It is further tested using the chi-square test 12 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .14. The data showed that the number of years in teaching among teachers cannot affect their teaching performance. Teachers perform well regardless of their number of years in teaching.

Table 21
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Promotion Rate
n=851

		Age								Total	
		20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 34	35 - 39	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59		60 - 64
Promotion Rate	Very Poor	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Poor	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	3
	Fair	12	11	4	2	3	2	2	1	0	37
	Good	39	136	92	93	100	41	30	24	7	562
	Excellent	15	59	46	55	40	9	12	6	6	248
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	59.063 ^a	32	.002
Likelihood Ratio	46.824	32	.044
Linear-by-Linear Association	.874	1	.350
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 24 cells (53.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

Table 21 shows the significant degree of relationship between promotion rate and age profile of the respondents. Based on the given result, it shows that across all age bracket of the respondent five hundred sixty-two teachers rated Good on the Promotion rate, two hundred forty-eight for Excellent, thirty-seven for Fair, three for Poor and one for Very Poor. It is then further tested using the Chi-square test and it shows that 24 cells (53.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02. This means that in terms of school performance there is a good rating of students from a cohort

enrolled in a grade at a given school year who enrolled in the next class in the following school.

Table 22
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Promotion Rate
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Promotion Rate	Very Poor	1	0	1
	Poor	0	3	3
	Fair	8	29	37
	Good	123	439	562
	Excellent	57	191	248
Total		189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.487 ^a	4	.344
Likelihood Ratio	4.643	4	.326
Linear-by-Linear Association	.029	1	.865
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22.

Table 22 shows the significant degree of relationship between promotion rate and sex of the respondents. Based on the given result, it shows that five hundred sixty-two teachers rated Good on the Promotion rate, two hundred forty-eight for Excellent, thirty-seven for Fair, three for Poor and one for Very Poor. It is then further tested using the Chi-square test. It shows that 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .22. There is a significant degree of relationship between promotion rate and sex profile of the respondents.

Table 23
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Promotion Rate
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Promotion Rate	Very Poor	1	0	1
	Poor	1	2	3
	Fair	19	18	37
	Good	165	397	562

Excellent	66	182	248
Total	252	599	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.874 ^a	4	.018
Likelihood Ratio	11.184	4	.025
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.895	1	.015
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

Table 23 shows that there is a significant degree of relationship between promotion rate and civil status of which five hundred sixty-two teachers rated Good on the Promotion rate, two hundred forty-eight for Excellent, thirty-seven for Fair, three for Poor and one for Very Poor. It is then further tested using the Chi-square test it shows that 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

Table 24
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and Promotion Rate
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Promotion Rate	Very Poor	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Poor	1	0	2	0	0	3
	Fair	10	22	5	0	0	37
	Good	190	289	57	23	3	562
	Excellent	101	108	24	11	4	248
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.773 ^a	16	.120
Likelihood Ratio	21.073	16	.176
Linear-by-Linear Association	.616	1	.433
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 15 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.

Table 24 shows the responses of teachers on the significant degree of relationship between promotion and highest educational attainment. Based on the result, five hundred sixty-two teachers rated Good on the Promotion rate, two hundred forty-eight for Excellent, thirty-seven for Fair, three for Poor and one for Very Poor. It is then further tested using the Chi-square test it shows that 15 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01. This means that there is a significant degree of relationship between promotion rate and highest educational attainment.

Table 25
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Number of Years in Teaching and Promotion Rate
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3	4 - 6	7 - 9	10 - 12	13 - 15	16 - 18	19 - 21	22 - 24	25 - 27	28 - 30	31 - 33		34 - 36
Promotion Rate	Very Poor	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Poor	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
	Fair	19	9	2	4	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	37
	Good	140	142	52	64	47	37	26	30	11	4	8	1	562
	Excellent	76	57	18	29	27	13	10	5	6	4	2	1	248
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	44.990 ^a	44	.430
Likelihood Ratio	47.609	44	.328
Linear-by-Linear Association	.086	1	.770
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 38 cells (63.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

Table 25 presents the responses of teachers on the relationship of promotion rate and number of years in teaching. With the result, it revealed that five hundred sixty-two teachers rated Good on the Promotion rate, two hundred forty-eight for Excellent, thirty-seven for Fair, three for Poor and one for Very Poor. It is then further tested using the Chi-

square test it shows that a. 38 cells (63.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

Table 26
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Failure Rate
n=851

		Age									Total
		20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 34	35 - 39	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59	60 - 64	
Failure Rate	Very Poor	22	36	27	42	34	9	12	4	2	188
	Poor	14	74	50	42	59	26	17	17	6	305
	Fair	25	51	32	36	21	10	10	8	3	196
	Good	5	44	31	26	27	8	5	2	2	150
	Excellent	0	2	3	4	3	0	0	0	0	12
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig.
Pearson Chi-Square	53.044 ^a	32	.011
Likelihood Ratio	56.750	32	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.523	1	.112
N of Valid Cases	851		

Table 26 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between failure rate and age profile. With the given result, it showed that three hundred five of the respondents are rated Poor on the failure rate and age, followed by one hundred ninety-six for Fair, one hundred eighty-eight for Very Poor, one hundred fifty for Good and twelve for Excellent. It is further tested with the aid for Chi-square test with which 13 cells (28.9%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18. This means that most of the teachers with regards to age have a unified idea that there is a poor rating on the failure rate in the school performance, which further means that there is an increase in the percentage of enrollees who failed each year level in a given school year.

Table 27
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Failure Rate
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Failure Rate	Very Poor	41	147	188
	Poor	73	232	305

Fair	37	159	196
Good	34	116	150
Excellent	4	8	12
Total	189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.680 ^a	4	.613
Likelihood Ratio	2.639	4	.620
Linear-by-Linear Association	.001	1	.975
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.67.

Table 27 presents the responses of the teachers' respondents in the significant relationship between failure rate and sex. With the given result, it showed that three hundred five of the respondents are rated Poor on the failure rate and age, followed by one hundred ninety-six for Fair, one hundred eighty-eight for Very Poor, one hundred fifty for Good and twelve for Excellent. It is further tested with the aid for Chi-square test with which 1 cell (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.67. There is a significant degree of relationship between the school performances particularly the failure rate and sex. With which it is further concluded based upon the result within terms of sex most of which rated an increase percentage of failure rate resulting to a Poor outcome.

Table 28
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Failure Rate
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Failure Rate	Very Poor	51	137	188
	Poor	77	228	305
	Fair	76	120	196
	Good	43	107	150
	Excellent	5	7	12
	Total	252	599	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.143 ^a	4	.016
Likelihood Ratio	11.800	4	.019
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.929	1	.087
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.55.

Table 28 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between failure rate and civil status. With the given result, it showed that three hundred five of the respondents are rated Poor on the failure rate and age, followed by one hundred ninety-six for Fair, one hundred eighty-eight for Very Poor, one hundred fifty for Good and twelve for Excellent. It is further tested with the aid for Chi-square test with which 1 cell (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.55. This means that most of the teachers regardless of civil status have a unified idea that there is a poor rating on the failure rate in the school performance, which further means that there is an increase percentage of enrollees who failed each year level in a given school year.

Table 29
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and Failure Rate
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Failure Rate	Very Poor	79	83	18	7	1	188
	Poor	98	154	31	19	3	305
	Fair	65	102	23	6	0	196
	Good	59	72	14	2	3	150
	Excellent	1	9	2	0	0	12
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.738 ^a	16	.121
Likelihood Ratio	25.381	16	.063
Linear-by-Linear Association	.019	1	.889
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 8 cells (32.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .10.

Table 29 presents the responses of the teachers' respondents in the significant relationship between failure rate and highest educational attainment. With the given result, it showed that three hundred five of the respondents are rated Poor on the failure rate and age, followed by one hundred ninety-six for Fair, one hundred eighty-eight for Very Poor, one hundred fifty for Good and twelve for Excellent. It is further tested with the aid for Chi-square test with which 8 cells (32.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .10. There is a significant degree of relationship between the school performances particularly the failure rate and sex. With which it is further concluded based upon the result within terms of highest educational attainment most of which rated an increase percentage of failure rate resulting to a Poor outcome.

Table 30
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Number of Years in Teaching and Failure Rate
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3	4 - 6	7 - 9	10- 12	13- 15	16- 18	19- 21	22- 24	25- 27	28- 30	31- 33		34- 36
Failure Rate	Very Poor	55	33	14	34	18	11	7	8	2	3	3	0	188
	Poor	72	81	23	27	24	24	18	18	7	5	5	1	305
	Fair	70	48	18	13	14	8	8	8	6	0	2	1	196
	Good	35	45	17	21	16	7	3	2	4	0	0	0	150
	Excellent	4	2	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	12
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	59.509 ^a	44	.059
Likelihood Ratio	67.408	44	.013
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.650	1	.017
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 27 cells (45.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

Table 30 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between failure rate and number of years in teaching. With the given result, it showed that three hundred five of the respondents are rated Poor on the failure rate and age, followed by one hundred ninety-six for Fair, one hundred eighty-eight for Very Poor, one

hundred fifty for Good and twelve for Excellent. It is further tested with the aid for Chi-square test with which a. 27 cells (45.0%) have been expected to count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03. This means that most of the teachers have a unified idea that there is a poor rating on the failure rate in the school performance, which further means that there is an increase percentage of enrollees who failed each year level in a given school year.

Table 31
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Retention Rate
n=851

		Age								Total	
		20 - 24	25 - 29	30 - 34	35 - 39	40 - 44	45 - 49	50 - 54	55 - 59		60 - 64
Retention Rate	Very Poor	17	45	27	42	26	8	8	9	6	188
	Poor	8	54	33	32	42	15	13	14	2	213
	Fair	15	29	24	25	12	10	6	4	2	127
	Good	19	61	47	42	50	14	14	3	3	253
	Excellent	7	18	12	9	14	6	3	1	0	70
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig.
Pearson Chi-Square	42.043 ^a	32	.110
Likelihood Ratio	44.493	32	.070
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.782	1	.095
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 9 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.07.

Table 31 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between retention rate and age. The result revealed that there were two hundred fifty-three teachers who rated Good on retention rate. It is then followed by two hundred thirteen for Poor rating, one hundred eighty-eight, Very Poor, one hundred twenty-seven Fair and seventy for Excellence. The result is further tested using the Chi-square test with which 9 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.07. This means that there is a Good performance within terms of enrolment in a school year that proceeds to the following year.

Table 32
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Retention Rate
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Retention Rate	Very Poor	32	156	188
	Poor	49	164	213
	Fair	23	104	127
	Good	65	188	253
	Excellent	20	50	70
Total		189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.658 ^a	4	.105
Likelihood Ratio	7.748	4	.101
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.023	1	.025
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 15.55.

Table 32 presents the responses of teachers in the significant relationship between retention rate and sex. The result revealed that there two hundred fifty-three teachers who rated Good on retention rate. It is then followed by two hundred thirteen for Poor rating, one hundred eighty-eight, Very Poor, one hundred twenty-seven Fair and seventy for Excellence. The result is further tested using the Chi-square test with which 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 15.55. This means that there is a Good performance within terms of enrolment in a school year that proceeds to the following year as per perceived by the respondents within terms of retention rate and sex.

Table 33
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Retention Rate
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Retention Rate	Very Poor	52	136	188
	Poor	56	157	213
	Fair	48	79	127

Good	74	179	253
Excellent	22	48	70
Total	252	599	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.678 ^a	4	.225
Likelihood Ratio	5.524	4	.238
Linear-by-Linear Association	.849	1	.357
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 20.73.

Table 33 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between retention rate and civil status. The result revealed that there two hundred fifty-three teachers who rated Good on retention rate. It is then followed by two hundred thirteen for Poor rating, one hundred eighty-eight, Very Poor, one hundred twenty-seven Fair and seventy for Excellence. The result is further tested using the Chi-square test with which a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 20.73. This means that there is a Good performance with in terms of retention rate as perceived by most of the teacher respondents.

Table 34
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and Retention Rate
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Retention Rate	Very Poor	77	87	17	6	1	188
	Poor	56	114	28	13	2	213
	Fair	48	64	11	4	0	127
	Good	88	128	27	6	4	253
	Excellent	33	27	5	5	0	70
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests

Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
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Pearson Chi-Square	25.349 ^a	16	.064
Likelihood Ratio	26.564	16	.047
Linear-by-Linear Association	.256	1	.613
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 6 cells (24.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .58.

Table 34 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between retention rate and highest educational attainment. The result revealed that there two hundred fifty-three teachers who rated Good on retention rate. It is then followed by two hundred thirteen for Poor rating, one hundred eighty-eight, Very Poor, one hundred twenty-seven Fair and seventy for Excellence. The result is further tested using the Chi-square test with which 6 cells (24.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .58. This means that there is a Good performance with in terms of enrolment in a school year that proceeds to the following year.

Table 35
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Numbers of years in Teaching and Retention Rate
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3	4 - 6	7 - 9	10 - 12	13 - 15	16 - 18	19 - 21	22 - 24	25 - 27	28 - 30	31 - 33		34 - 36
Retention Rate	Very Poor	52	41	14	31	16	8	9	8	1	2	6	0	188
	Poor	47	56	21	18	18	18	10	12	8	2	2	1	213
	Fair	46	33	7	13	8	3	6	8	3	0	0	0	127
	Good	66	60	26	29	27	18	9	5	6	4	2	1	253
	Excellent	25	19	4	6	5	4	3	3	1	0	0	0	70
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	52.280 ^a	44	.183
Likelihood Ratio	56.554	44	.097
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.062	1	.080
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 22 cells (36.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16.

Table 35 presents the responses of the respondents in the significant relationship between retention rate and number of years in teaching. The result revealed that there are two hundred fifty-three teachers who rated Good on retention rate. It is then followed by two hundred thirteen for Poor rating, one hundred eighty-eight, Very Poor, one hundred twenty-seven Fair and seventy for Excellent. The result is further tested using the Chi-square test with which 22 cells (36.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .16. This means that there is a Good performance within terms of retention rate as perceived by most of the teacher respondents.

Table 36
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Age and Drop-out Rate
n=851

		Age								Total	
		20 – 24	25 - 29	30 – 34	35 – 39	40 - 44	45 – 49	50 - 54	55 - 59		60 - 64
Drop-Out Rate	Very Poor	29	56	41	56	52	14	13	10	6	277
	Poor	12	79	46	42	48	20	17	15	5	284
	Fair	21	29	28	28	21	11	8	4	2	152
	Good	3	41	24	23	21	8	6	2	0	128
	Excellent	1	2	4	1	2	0	0	0	0	10
Total		66	207	143	150	144	53	44	31	13	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46.507 ^a	32	.047
Likelihood Ratio	50.504	32	.020
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.808	1	.094
N of Valid Cases		851	

Table 36 shows the responses of the teacher respondents in the significant relationship between drop-out rate and age profile. As revealed in the result, it showed that there are two hundred eighty-four teacher respondents who have given a Poor remarks on the drop-out rate and age. It is then followed by two hundred seventy-seven for Very Poor, one hundred fifty-two for Fair, one hundred twenty-eight for Good and ten for Excellent remarks. Using the Chi-square test there is 14 cells (31.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .15. Most of the respondents responded that the there is an increase of students percentage who leave school during the year as well as those who complete a certain level but fail to enroll in the next grade/year level as visible in a Poor remarks with the highest in rank.

Table 37
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Sex and Drop-out Rate
n=851

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Drop-Out Rate	Very Poor	61	216	277
	Poor	68	216	284
	Fair	31	121	152
	Good	29	99	128
	Excellent	0	10	10
Total		189	662	851

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.660 ^a	4	.454
Likelihood Ratio	5.825	4	.213
Linear-by-Linear Association	.348	1	.555
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.22.

Table 37 presents the responses of the teachers in the significant relationship between drop-out rate and sex. Based upon the result it showed that there are two hundred eighty-four teacher respondents who have given a Poor remarks on the drop-out rate and sex. It is then followed by two hundred seventy-seven for Very Poor, one hundred fifty-two for Fair, one hundred twenty-eight for Good and ten for Excellent remarks. Using the Chi-square test there is 1 cell (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.22. Most of the respondents responded that there is an increase of student's drop-out percentage as for its Poor remarks.

Table 38
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Civil Status and Drop-out Rate
n=851

		Civil Status		Total
		Single	Married	
Drop-Out Rate	Very Poor	71	206	277
	Poor	85	199	284
	Fair	56	96	152
	Good	38	90	128
	Excellent	2	8	10
Total		252	599	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.375 ^a	4	.173
Likelihood Ratio	6.315	4	.177
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.789	1	.181
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.96.

Table 38 shows the responses of the teacher respondents in the significant relationship between drop-out rate and civil status. As revealed in the result, it showed that there are two hundred eighty-four teacher respondents who have given a Poor remarks on the drop-out rate and age. It is then followed by two hundred seventy-seven for Very Poor, one hundred fifty-two for Fair, one hundred twenty-eight for Good and ten for Excellent remarks. It is further tested using the Chi-square test there is 1 cell (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.96. Most of the respondents responded that there is an increase of student's percentage who leave school during the year as well as those who complete a certain level but fail to enroll in the next grade/year level as visible in a Poor remarks with the highest in rank.

Table 39
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and Drop-out Rate
n=851

		Highest educational attainment					Total
		Bachelor's Degree	With MA Units	MA Degree Holder	With PhD Units	PhD Degree Holder	
Drop-Out Rate	Very Poor	114	131	22	8	2	277
	Poor	88	139	34	20	3	284
	Fair	53	75	20	4	0	152
	Good	46	68	10	2	2	128
	Excellent	1	7	2	0	0	10
Total		302	420	88	34	7	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.456 ^a	16	.062
Likelihood Ratio	26.988	16	.042
Linear-by-Linear Association	.575	1	.448
N of Valid Cases	851		

a. 9 cells (36.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.

Table 39 shows the responses of the teacher respondents in the significant relationship between drop-out rate and highest educational attainment. As revealed in the result, it showed that there are two hundred eighty-four teacher respondents who have given a Poor remarks on the drop-out rate and age. It is then followed by two hundred seventy-seven for Very Poor, one hundred fifty-two for Fair, one hundred twenty-eight for Good and ten for Excellent remarks. Using the Chi-square test there are 9 cells (36.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08. Most of the respondents responded that the there is an increase of student's percentage who leave school during the year as well as those who complete a certain level but fail to enroll in the next grade/year level as visible in a Poor remarks with the highest in rank.

Table 40
Significant Degree of Relationship Between Number of Years in Teaching and Drop-out Rate
n=851

		Number of years in teaching											Total	
		0 - 3	4 - 6	7 - 9	10 - 12	13 - 15	16 - 18	19 - 21	22 - 24	25 - 27	28 - 30	31 - 33		34 - 36
Drop- Out Rate	Very Poor	81	58	15	45	22	17	17	11	4	3	3	1	277
	Poor	74	74	27	22	26	17	11	16	6	5	6	0	284
	Fair	48	35	15	13	12	9	5	7	6	0	1	1	152
	Good	27	42	15	15	14	6	4	2	3	0	0	0	128
	Excellent	6	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Total		236	209	72	97	74	51	37	36	19	8	10	2	851

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	59.346 ^a	44	.061
Likelihood Ratio	66.565	44	.016
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.866	1	.090
N of Valid Cases		851	

a. 26 cells (43.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02.

Table 40 presents the responses of the teachers in the significant relationship between drop-out rate and number of years in teaching. Based upon the result, it showed that there are two hundred eighty-four teacher respondents who have given a Poor remarks on the drop-out rate and number of years in teaching. It is then followed by two hundred seventy-seven for Very Poor, one hundred fifty-two for Fair, one hundred twenty-eight for Good and ten for Excellent remarks. Using the Chi-square test there are 26 cells

(43.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .02. Most of the respondents responded that there is an increase of student's drop-out percentage as for its Poor remarks.

Findings

The study presents the following findings according to sequence of the specific sub-problems.

1. **Demographic Profile of Respondents.** The study revealed that out of 851 respondents, the majority were aged 25–29 years old, predominantly female, and mostly married. Most of the teacher respondents were taking up units toward a Master's degree, and their teaching experience ranged from 0 to 3 years.
2. **In-Service Training (INSET).** Among the five indicators evaluated under INSET, the areas that received the least attention during implementation were identifying subject area competencies not covered in the first two quarters, and capacitating teachers with diverse teaching strategies to enhance classroom delivery.
3. **Learning Action Cell (LAC).** Under LAC, the least focused items were the identification of further training in subject-matter content and the enhancement of teacher competence in applying effective teaching strategies.
4. **Division Mass Training.** In terms of Division Mass Training, the aspects that were least emphasized included the effectiveness of training management and the appropriateness of the training methodologies used.
5. **Regional Mass Training.** Findings showed that during Regional Mass Training, the least focused areas were the promotion of a culture of collegial and collaborative learning among teachers and the understanding of individual student differences to support optimal development.
6. **Effectiveness of Teacher Training Modalities.** When comparing the four training modalities, INSET received the highest rating with a mean of 4.0063 and a standard deviation of 0.55137, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. It was followed by Division Mass Training, LAC, and Regional Mass Training, which received the lowest rating due to limited participation and inconsistent knowledge dissemination.
7. **Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Training.** The overall effectiveness of teachers' training was rated as Very Satisfactory, indicating a positive reception and usefulness of training efforts among the respondents.
8. **Teachers' Performance in Teaching.** In terms of teaching, the lowest-ranked indicator was the preparation and use of audio-visual aids, while the highest was promoting teamwork and idea-sharing among students.

9. **Teachers' Performance on Students' Needs.** The aspect ranked lowest was the ability to produce independent learners, whereas the highest-ranked was helping students understand important ideas.
10. **Teachers' Performance on Students' Evaluation.** Assigning appropriate homework received the lowest rating, while the proper use of various evaluation techniques or tests was rated highest.
11. **Teachers' Performance in Classroom Management.** The least-rated behavior was the effective use of punishment to reduce undesirable actions, while the highest was proper record keeping.
12. **Teachers' Performance on Human Relationships.** The establishment of appropriate teacher-student relationships received the lowest rating, while showing support and care for students received the highest.
13. **Teachers' Characteristics.** Among teacher characteristics, the lowest-rated was the promptness in providing test results, while the highest was the demonstration of good manners in the classroom.
14. **Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation.** Students' ease of understanding the lesson ranked lowest, while the clarity and audibility of the teacher's voice ranked highest.
15. **Student Interest and Involvement in Learning.** Stimulating student thinking received the lowest rating, while the ability to sense when students are bored was rated highest.
16. **Teacher-Student Relationship.** The item rated lowest was entering the classroom with a smiling and agreeable face, while treating all students equally received the highest rating.
17. **Summary of Teaching Performance.** Among all the indicators, the teacher-student relationship emerged as the highest-rated dimension, while training effectiveness in terms of students' evaluation received the lowest score.
18. **Overall Teaching Performance.** The respondents rated their overall teaching performance as Excellent.
19. **School Performance: Promotion Rate.** The promotion rate was generally rated as Good by the teacher respondents.
20. **School Performance: Failure Rate.** Respondents gave a Poor rating for the failure rate in their respective schools.

21. **School Performance: Retention Rate.** The retention rate received a Good rating from most respondents.
22. **School Performance: Dropout Rate.** The dropout rate was rated Poor by the teacher respondents.
23. **Overall School Performance.** Despite mixed results on individual indicators, the overall school performance was rated as Excellent.
24. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Teachers' Performance.** There was a significant correlation between the level of effectiveness of teachers' training and teachers' performance, indicating that training positively affects performance.
25. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Promotion Rate.** The findings showed a significant relationship between the level of teachers' training and promotion rate, suggesting that teacher development leads to increased student promotion.
26. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Failure Rate.** A significant relationship was found between teachers' training and failure rate, implying that improved training reduces student failure.
27. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Retention Rate.** There was a significant correlation between the level of training and retention rate, showing that training supports student continuity.
28. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and Dropout Rate.** Findings indicated a significant relationship between training effectiveness and dropout rate, meaning better training may help reduce school dropouts.
29. **Correlation Between Teachers' Training and School Performance.** A significant correlation existed between the level of training and overall school performance, proving that effective training enhances school outcomes.
30. **Relationship Between Teachers' Profile and Training Effectiveness.** The study found that age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and years in teaching all had significant relationships with the level of training effectiveness.
31. **Relationship Between Teachers' Profile and Performance.** There was also a significant relationship between teachers' profiles and their performance, indicating that demographic and professional background influences effectiveness.
32. **Relationship Between Teachers' Profile and School Performance.** Teacher profile variables were significantly associated with school performance, with most respondents providing uniform Good ratings.

33. **Relationship Between Teachers' Performance and Promotion Rate.** A significant correlation was observed between teachers' performance and promotion rate, suggesting that better performance leads to improved student progression.
34. **Relationship Between Teachers' Performance and Failure Rate.** A significant relationship was found between teachers' performance and failure rate, meaning improved teacher performance reduces failure.
35. **Relationship Between Teachers' Performance and Retention Rate.** There was a significant correlation between performance and retention rate, indicating that strong teacher performance encourages students to stay in school.
36. **Relationship Between Teachers' Performance and Dropout Rate.** Teachers' performance was significantly related to the dropout rate, where stronger performance was associated with fewer dropouts.
37. **Relationship Between Teachers' Performance and School Performance.** A significant correlation was observed between teachers' performance and overall school performance, highlighting the impact of quality teaching on institutional outcomes.
38. **Variance in Training Effectiveness.** The study showed a significant variance in the level of effectiveness across different types of training, meaning each training program had varying levels of impact.
39. **Variance in Teachers' Performance.** There was a significant variance in performance across the different teaching dimensions, confirming that teacher effectiveness is not uniform across all areas.
40. **Variance in School Performance Indicators.** The results indicated a significant variance in the different indicators of school performance, showing that some aspects of school functioning were stronger than others.

Conclusions

The findings emphasize the need for school administrators to ensure that teachers are regularly included in Regional Mass Trainings, which were rated least effective among the various training modalities. Likewise, stricter and more consistent implementation of Learning Action Cell (LAC) activities is recommended, as this too ranked low in training effectiveness. Each level of training, from LAC to Regional, must address specific concerns such as enhancing subject-matter content, identifying uncovered competencies, improving training management, and fostering a culture of collegiality among educators. In terms of teachers' performance, the area of student evaluation, particularly the assignment of appropriate homework, was identified as the weakest and should be targeted through focused training. School performance indicators revealed

Poor ratings for both failure and dropout rates, suggesting these areas require immediate attention from stakeholders. Regardless of demographic profiles, all teachers can benefit from continuous training, which positively influences both their performance and the school's overall effectiveness. The study further affirms that teachers' training impacts various dimensions of performance and that increased training participation correlates with better teaching outcomes and improved school metrics. Each training level contributes differently to effectiveness, just as teaching performance varies across multiple dimensions. Likewise, school performance shows variation across indicators, indicating strengths in some areas and weaknesses in others. Finally, the interrelationship among training effectiveness, teaching performance, and school indicators such as promotion, failure, retention, and dropout rates reflects a symmetrical data pattern, confirming that these dimensions significantly influence each other.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following measures are recommended:

1. The findings of the study should be presented to the stakeholders of the school, they deserve to know.
2. Proper planning on the topics, subjects or issues to be addressed in any level of trainings.
3. Teachers must also be given the chance to attend Regional Mass Training to be more capacitated towards teaching.
4. Revisit the memorandum on the conduct of Learning Action Cell for full implementation of the said memorandum.
5. Consensus from the teachers on the issues and concerns from the field for it to be addressed during the conduct of a training which will benefit themselves.
6. A collaborative effort of the school administrators, teachers and other stakeholders must be utilized for a better school performance leading to great achievements of the learners.
7. Train teachers in a much more comprehensive and up to date teaching techniques for a better teaching performance.
8. The proposed enhancement program will be implemented as early as possible to address the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to ethical research protocols and standards. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained the necessary approvals from the University of Bohol, including permissions from the Dean of the Graduate Studies and the Vice President for Academics. The research instrument was pilot-tested to ensure its validity, and the original authors of the adapted questionnaire were duly acknowledged and contacted for authorization.

Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all respondents. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, and that the data collected would be used solely for academic and research purposes. The research was also subjected to ethics review procedures as mandated by the Research Ethics Committee of the university, thereby ensuring that all protocols concerning the rights and welfare of the respondents were upheld throughout the study.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

Rationale

Education is the ability to meet life's situation, it is a character building process, enhancing one's personality and making him/her rational, capable responsive and intelligent. There are factors affecting student performance, investigating the variables of teacher, student, parents and community and therefore concluded that the teacher was the key factor in student and even school achievements. The quality of education depends on the quality of teachers, particularly in the initial stages of education.

Training plays an important role in improving the quality of education in schools. The professional quality of the trained teacher depends on the quality of the curriculum to which the teacher was exposed and the ways it is implemented. With this, teacher effectiveness depends on how well a teacher performs in the classroom and this is dependent on how competent the teacher is. Teaching competence also bears the marks of perception, value and beliefs that the individual carries when she enters teacher training program.

In connection to this, school performance will also be based on the quality of teacher. And with that, it is a mere indication, that the higher the performance of the school, the better the teaching forces. Therefore, it is a collaborative work of the school stakeholders to assess the effectiveness of teachers' training to its school performance.

Objectives

This enhancement program measures to seek:

1. Immediate dissemination of the study to ensure full comprehension on the effectiveness of teachers training in relation to teacher and school performance.
2. Creation of schedule for enhancement programs to cater the needs of teachers in teaching performance.
3. To encourage teachers to attend or participate in trainings to become effective and efficient in the teaching and learning process.
4. This program must be functional and sustained with full cooperation among teachers and higher authorities.

Mechanics of Implementation

The proposed enhancement program will be presented to the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of Bohol for further perusal. The guidelines for the implementation of the said enhancement program are as follows:

1. A copy of the program will be presented to the administration of the University of Bohol for Approval.
2. After the approval from the institution, it will be forwarded to the school district supervisor under study.
3. The proposed enhancement program would then be assessed and evaluated so that present weaknesses would be corrected and strong points could be enhanced.

Schedule of Implementation

The implementation of the proposed improvement measures should start in the next school year to come.

Evaluative Measures

The status of progress of the improvement measures may be monitored assessed at the end of every school year so that any deficiencies, update or modification could be corrected or implemented immediately.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

AREAS OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	DATE	FUNDING SOURCE	PERSONS INVOLVED	EXPECTED OUTCOME
Topics/Issues in Any Level of Training						
INSET	To identify subject area competencies not covered in the first two quarters	Gather data from schools and its consolidation	End of the 2 nd quarter	None	Teachers and School Administrators	Consolidated competencies not covered in the first two quarters
	To capacitate teachers on the different teaching strategies and other related activities to improve the delivery of teaching	Seminars, training and workshops Seminars, training and workshops	October	MOOE	School Administrators, Teachers, Resource Person	New learnings on the different teaching strategies in the

						delivery of teaching
Division Mass Training	To have an effectiveness of training management		Whole year round	MOOE	School Administrators	New methods of training management
	To ensure appropriateness of training methodologies	Seminars, training and workshops	Whole year round	MOOE	Administrators, teachers	
Learning Action Cell	To identify further training on subject-matter content	FGD, conferences	Twice a month	MOOE	Administrators, Subject Specialist, teachers	A knowledgeable educator
	To enhance teacher competence in the use of strategies		October	MOOE		
Regional Mass Training	To promote a culture of collegial and collaborative learning among teachers in the entire region	Workshops, Training and seminars	Whole year round	MOOE	Resource Person, Administrators, teachers	A more capacitated administrator and teachers.
	To understand the significance of the individual differences of child and to take appropriate steps for their optimum development					
Dimensions in Teaching Performance						
Teachers' performance in terms of students' evaluation	To ensure proper giving of students homework.	Checking of DLL for its alignment to the competencies	Everyday	None	School Principal, teachers	Checked DLL
Teachers' performance in classroom management	To employ an effective use of punishment for decreasing undesirable behavior	Classroom Observation	Once a month	None	School administrator, teachers, students	Classroom Observation Tool

Clarity and Effectiveness of Presentation	To let the students understand easily what the teachers are saying	Technical assistance	As the need arises	None	School Administrators and teachers	
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